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Regenerative medicine and stem cell therapies became needs for continuously improving human condition, exploring new frontiers of research and applying the progress in clinical translation.

From basic science in stem cell genomics, genomic reprogramming, epigenetics and tissue development to novel technologies in clinical translations of regenerative therapy in mankind perspec-

tive, our scientific community must be better “articulated”, i.e., better organized and sustained.

In fact, the theory of general competitive equilibrium, public economic theory, altruism, ethics and topics of economic anthropology, i.e., the economics of regenerative medicine, must be better supported by combining public funding and market funding for industrial development and large scale production and sale.

Our global problems will be solved through science-based solutions, and together we can do more for improving our health. With these thoughts, there are several simple questions addressed to researchers in the field of brain organization and function. What cell type is the pial cell? What contribution has this cell in the regeneration and repairing of brain tissue with stem cells? In my opinion, a special interstitial cell, named by my research team a “cordocyte”, ubiquitous located in brain, with local specializations (including the pia mater as a pial cell) and multiple functions – facilitating benefic processes and delaying pathological processes – is a general supervisor and a good candidate for stem cell therapy, cooperating with stem cells in many situations. In the last instance, the brain performance improves if its microenvironment is maintained under appropriate conditions, for which cordocytes are responsible.